

Heterocyclization of some chalcones to isoxazoles, pyrazoles and pyrimidine nuclei under microwave irradiation and their biological profile[†]

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Abstract : Rapid and efficient methods for the preparation of a set of isoxazole, pyrazole and pyrimidine derivatives of imidazolinone and quinazolinone by the reaction of 5-substituted arylidene-{2-(imidazolyl/quinazolyl)imino}thiazolidinone (chalcones) with hydroxylamine, urea and hydrazine hydrate under MWI are reported. Excellent yields and higher purity are obtained in MW enhanced synthesis as compared to the conventional procedure which required exceedingly long reaction times, high temperatures and tedious workups. The potent antimicrobial effects of the synthesized compounds were investigated.

Keywords : Chalcones, isoxazoles, pyrazoles, pyrimidines, thiazolidinones.

Introduction

MAOS¹ (Microwave Assisted Organic Synthesis) strategies offer feasible solutions as their benefits are manifold : it frequently leads to dramatically reduced reaction times, higher yields, cleaner reaction profiles and above all eco-friendliness. One fact that a "yes or no answer" for a particular chemical transformation can often be obtained within 5 to 10 min (as compared to several hours in a conventional protocol) has contributed significantly to the acceptance of microwave chemistry both in industry and academia. In view this, we planned to apply this new methodology in our research work aiming at the heterocyclization of chalcones.

As our interest in "search for bioactive heterocycles", we sought unexplored, synthetically accessible heterocyclic templates (imidazolinone and quinazolinones) capable of bearing some potential pharmacophores to elicit and enhance the inherent biological activity. The systematic propagation of heterocyclic rings in imidazolinones and quinazolinones precursors with the installation of biologically active heterocyclic units such as isoxazoles, pyrimidine and pyrazoles is the major focal point of the present investigation. Pyrimidines are found to be endowed with

potential therapeutic activities such as antitumor², antiviral³, antimycobacterial⁴, anticancer, analgesic⁵, antifolate⁶, antimicrobial⁷, antiproliferate⁸, antihistaminic⁹ activities and many others. Isoxazoles are widely investigated for therapeutic uses, especially as tranquilizing agent and central nervous system (CNS) regulatant and are reported to have bactericidal¹⁰, bacteriostatic and fungicidal activities^{11,12}. Pyrazoles display a number of antimicrobial activities like antitumor¹³, immunosuppressive¹⁴, antibacterial¹⁵, antiinflammatory¹⁶, anticancer¹⁷, antidiabetic¹⁸ and antidepressants¹⁹. The imidazolinone moiety is a useful functionality for the development of biologically interesting molecules and quinazolinones represent well known pharmacophoric scaffolds with a wide portfolio of interesting physiological activities such as hypotensive²⁰, antimalarial²¹, anti-parkinson²², anticonvulsant²³, antihypnotic²⁴ and antihypertensive²⁵ activities.

Thus the coupling of this elegant MORE (Microwave Oriented Reaction Enhancement) synthesis with a wide spectrum of the biological activity of targeted compounds would be expected to afford interesting series of compounds. The results of microwave heating are compared with conventionally heated transformations.

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

Results and discussion

The high throughput achieved by microwave technology is exemplified by the successful synthesis of the target compounds through a multistep reaction procedure. The experimental procedure consists of reacting an intimately ground equimolar proportion of azalactone **1a** and benzoxazinone **1b** with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol furnishing the corresponding imidazolinone **2a** and quinazolinone **2b**, respectively. Spectral data were recorded to confirm the structure of these products. Compound **2a** exhibits a coupled vibration at 3282 and 3280 cm^{-1} due to $-\text{NH}_2$ protons in its IR spectrum. It also displayed a singlet for two protons around δ 5.45 assigned for $-\text{NH}_2$ protons and at δ 6.52 for exo-olefinic proton. The imidazolinone nucleus also manifested characteristic bands at 1655 and 1625 cm^{-1} for C=O and C=N groups, respectively. Similarly, the IR spectrum of quinazolinone **2b** showed bands at 3292, 3290 (coupled vibration for $-\text{NH}_2$), 1660 and 1630 cm^{-1} for C=O and C=N groups, respectively. The reaction of **2a** and **2b** with potassium thiocyanate gave the corresponding imidazolyl and quinazolyl thiourea **3a/3b**, the structures of which were confirmed by the appearance of additional C=S bands at around 1228 cm^{-1} (for **3a**) and 1232 cm^{-1} (for **3b**), respectively. These were further allowed to react with chloroacetic acid and sodium acetate in acetic anhydride followed by subsequent *in situ* cyclization of the intermediate compounds to give the corresponding thiazolidinones **4**. The ^1H NMR of **4a** compound showed a sharp singlet at around δ 3.34 due to two protons of the $\text{CH}_2\text{-S}$ group. Its IR spectra showed the disappearance of coupled vibrations and appearance of bands for C-S-C, C=O and N-H, at around 685, 1720 and 3300 cm^{-1} , respectively (Scheme 1).

The thiazolidinone moiety possesses an active methylene group, which undergoes a Knoevenagel condensation with active carbonyl compounds like *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and *p*-fluorobenzaldehyde to give the chalcones **5**. The formation of compounds **5** was confirmed by the absence of very intense peak of $\text{CH}_2\text{-S}$ group in compounds **4** due to condensation with substituted benzaldehyde. A slight shift of band for C=O from 1720 cm^{-1} (in **4a**) to 1705 cm^{-1} (in **5a**) is due to conjugation.

Heterocyclization of these compounds with various binucleophiles viz. hydroxylamine, hydrazine hydrate and urea afforded their respective *in situ* oxidized products **6**,

7 and **8**. The driving force for this *in situ* oxidation is the formation of new heterocyclic rings. The disappearance of the carbonyl frequency in IR spectrum for **6** and **7** confirms the installation of isoxazole and pyrazole moieties.

In case of **8a**¹ the band at around 1715 cm^{-1} was assigned to the new amidic carbonyl group. However, the ^1H NMR spectrum of **7a**¹ shows an additional signal at around δ 6.20 for N-H proton, Similarly, a singlet at around δ 9.41 was observed for the amidic -NH proton in the ^1H NMR of compound **8a**¹ (Scheme 2). Finally, conclusive evidence has been gathered from the Mass spectra of all final compounds.

Physical and analytical data of all the synthesized compounds are given in Table 1.

Antimicrobial activity :

Six compounds were screened *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activities against two strains of bacteria (*Proteus mirabilis*, *Bacillus subtilis*) and two strains of fungi (*Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*) using the disc diffusion method. Commercial antimicrobial Ciprofloxacin and antifungal Amphotericin were also screened under similar conditions for comparison. The results have been tabulated in the form of inhibition zones and activity index in Table 2.

The results revealed that all tested compounds exhibit moderate to strong activity against both fungi and *P. mirabilis* and are less active against *B. subtilis*. Compounds **6a**¹, **6a**², **6b**², **7b**² and **8b**¹ shows considerable potency against *C. albicans* while against *A. fumigatus* they are moderately active. Compounds **7a**¹, **7b**¹ and **7a**² are showing strong activity against both fungi. Similarly, compounds **8a**¹, **8a**² and **8b**² are found to show excellent activity against *P. mirabilis* while against *B. subtilis*, they are showing moderate activity. Remaining compounds exhibited moderate activity as compared to the standard.

Experimental

All reactions were carried out in a domestic microwave oven (Kenstar, Model no. OM-26 EGO). Melting points are uncorrected and determined in open capillaries. Reactions were monitored by thin layer chromatography using silica gel-G as adsorbent using ethyl acetate : *n*-hexane (7 : 3) as eluent and was detected by iodine vapors. IR spectra (KBr pellets) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1800 (FTIR) spectrometer. ^1H NMR spec-

Scheme 1

tra (DMSO- d_6) were taken on a Bruker DRX spectrometer (300 MHz FT NMR) using TMS as internal standard and chemical shifts are expressed in δ . Mass spectra were taken on a Jeol SX-102/PA-6000 (EI) spectrometer. Elemental analyses for C, H and N were conducted using a Perkin-Elmer C, H, N analyzer : their results were found to be in good agreement with the calculated values ($\pm 0.2\%$). The starting compounds **1a**²⁶ and **1b**²⁷ are prepared according to reported method.

General procedure for the preparation of imidazolone 2a and quinazolinone 2b :

Conventional method : Compound **1a/1b** (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (20 mL). Hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 1–2 h.

After the completion of reaction and cooling, the white solid was filtered and recrystallized from EtOH to give **2a** and **2b** in 65–69% yields.

Microwave method : A slurry of compound **1a/1b** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in absolute alcohol was exposed to microwave irradiation in an open Erlenmeyer flask for 1–2 min. It was cooled; the white precipitate was filtered. Recrystallization from EtOH afforded **2a** and **2b** in 74–75% yields.

1-Amino-4-benylidene-2-phenylimidazolone-5-one (2a, C₁₆H₁₃N₃O) :

White powder (75%); m.p. 170 °C; IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3282–3280 (NH₂), 3080 (C–H, aromatic), 1655 (C=O), 1625 (C=N), 1560 (C–N) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (DMSO- d_6) :

2-8	a		b	
R				
5-8	a ¹	a ²	b ¹	b ²
Ar	p-C ₆ H ₄ -F	m-C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂	p-C ₆ H ₄ -F	m-C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂

Scheme 2

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of compounds

Compd.	Molecular formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%) MW (con)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
				Calcd. (Found)			S
				C	H	N	
2a	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	170	75	73.00	4.94	15.96	-
			(69)	(72.97)	(4.91)	(15.93)	
2b	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O	220	74	70.88	4.64	17.72	-
			(65)	(70.84)	(4.62)	(17.69)	

Table-1 (contd.)

3a	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS	180	73 (64)	63.35 (63.31)	4.34 (4.32)	17.39 (17.37)	9.93 (9.90)
3b	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS	230	70 (62)	60.81 (60.79)	4.05 (4.02)	18.91 (18.89)	10.81 (10.79)
4a	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	190	77 (69)	62.98 (62.91)	3.86 (3.82)	15.46 (15.42)	9.24 (9.21)
4b	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	121	75 (64)	63.35 (63.31)	3.72 (3.68)	13.04 (13.01)	9.93 (9.89)
5a ¹	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ SF	184	87 (69)	66.66 (66.62)	3.63 (3.60)	11.96 (11.92)	6.83 (6.80)
5b ¹	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ SF	178	76 (63)	67.28 (67.24)	3.50 (3.46)	9.81 (9.75)	7.47 (7.43)
5a ²	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄ S	195	85 (72)	63.03 (63.00)	3.43 (3.39)	14.14 (14.11)	6.46 (6.42)
5b ²	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₄ S	181	83 (73)	63.29 (63.25)	3.29 (3.26)	12.30 (12.27)	7.03 (6.99)
6a ¹	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₂ SF	226	79 (65)	64.73 (64.96)	3.52 (3.46)	14.50 (14.47)	6.62 (6.58)
6b ¹	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₂ SF	192	83 (67)	51.58 (51.55)	3.39 (3.36)	12.66 (12.62)	7.22 (7.19)
6a ²	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄ S	207	70 (59)	61.29 (61.27)	3.33 (3.30)	16.50 (16.46)	6.27 (6.23)
6b ²	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄ S	189	74 (62)	61.40 (61.36)	3.19 (3.14)	14.92 (14.88)	6.80 (6.76)
7a ¹	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₆ OSF	231	76 (60)	64.73 (64.69)	3.94 (3.91)	17.42 (17.38)	6.63 (6.59)
7b ¹	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₆ OSF	160	74 (63.11)	63.15 (63.11)	3.72 (3.68)	18.42 (18.39)	7.01 (6.97)
7a ²	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₃ S	190	69 (61.26)	61.29 (61.26)	3.73 (3.70)	19.25 (19.21)	6.63 (6.57)
7b ²	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₃ S	183	73 (59.59)	59.62 (59.59)	3.51 (3.48)	20.28 (20.26)	6.62 (6.59)
8a ¹	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₆ O ₂ SF	184	74 (63.49)	63.52 (63.49)	3.72 (3.69)	16.47 (16.45)	6.27 (6.24)
8b ¹	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ SF	183	75 (61.96)	61.98 (61.96)	3.51 (3.48)	17.35 (17.32)	6.61 (6.58)
8a ²	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₄ S	207	76 (60.30)	60.33 (60.30)	3.53 (3.50)	18.24 (18.20)	5.95 (5.92)
8b ²	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₄ S	195	74 (58.68)	58.70 (58.68)	3.32 (3.30)	19.17 (19.14)	6.26 (6.23)

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of some synthesized compounds

Compd.	Zone of inhibition (mm) (activity index) ^a			
	Antifungal activity (500 ppm)		Antibacterial activity (500 ppm)	
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>
6a ¹	16 (0.80)	11 (0.69)	19 (0.76)	16 (0.70)
6a ²	18 (0.90)	25 (1.56)	22 (0.88)	19 (0.83)
6b ¹	20 (1.0)	18 (1.13)	16 (0.64)	21 (0.91)
6b ²	15 (0.75)	21 (1.31)	25 (1.00)	13 (0.56)
7a ¹	25 (1.25)	27 (1.69)	5 (0.20)	14 (0.61)
7a ²	27 (1.35)	27 (1.35)	0.0 (0)	15 (0.65)
7b ¹	22 (1.1)	22 (1.38)	18 (0.72)	11 (0.47)
7b ²	13 (0.65)	24 (1.50)	21 (0.84)	14 (0.60)
8a ¹	16 (0.80)	0.0 (0)	26 (1.04)	17 (0.74)
8a ²	11 (0.55)	12 (0.75)	35 (1.40)	18 (0.78)
8b ¹	18 (0.90)	19 (1.18)	24 (0.96)	22 (0.95)
8b ²	19 (0.95)	15 (0.94)	29 (1.16)	20 (0.86)
C ₁	20	16	-	-
C ₂	-	-	25	23

^aActivity index = Inhibition area of the sample/inhibition area of the standard.

Standard : C₁ = Amphotericin, C₂ = Ciprofloxacin.

δ 7.22–6.71 (10H, m, Ar-H), 6.52 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 5.45 (2H, s, NH₂) ppm.

3-Amino-2-phenylquinazolin-4-(4H)-one (**2b**, C₁₄H₁₁N₃O) :

Shining white powder (74%); m.p. 220 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3292–3290 (NH₂), 3000 (C–H aromatic), 1660 (C=O), 1630 (C=N), 1572 (C–N) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.61–7.02 (9H, m, Ar-H), 5.55 (2H, s, NH₂) ppm.

General procedure for the preparation of imidazolyl/quinazolyl thiourea 3a, 3b :

Conventional method : Refluxing a mixture of **2a/2b** in DMF (0.002 mol) and potassium thiocyanate (0.008 mol) in dil. HCl (2 mL in 10 mL of water) for 4 to 6 h yielded a yellow coloured solution that was poured into ice-cold water and stirred well. The solid separated was recrystallized from EtOH in 62–64% yields.

Microwave method : A mixture of **2a/2b** in DMF (0.002 mol) and potassium thiocyanate (0.008 mol) in dilute hydrochloric acid (2.0 mL in 10.0 mL of water) was subjected to microwave irradiation in an open Erlenmeyer flask for 3–6 min. The yellow coloured solution obtained was poured into water. The solid separated was recrystallized from EtOH in 70–73% yields.

1-[4-Benzylidene-5-oxo-2-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-1-yl]thiourea (**3a**, C₁₇H₁₄N₄OS) :

Yellowish powder (73%); m.p. 180 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3218–3222 (N–H), 3086 (C–H, aromatic), 1663 (C=O), 1621 (C=N), 1228 (C=S) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.81–6.45 (10H, m, Ar-H), 6.26 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 5.24 (1H, s, -NH), 4.32 (2H, s, -NH₂) ppm.

1-[4-Oxo-2-phenyl quinazolin-3(4H)-yl]thiourea (**3b**, C₁₅H₁₂N₄OS) :

Pale yellow powder (70%); m.p. 230 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3292–3296 (N–H), 3115 (C–H, aromatic), 1668 (C=O), 1628 (C=N), 1232 (C=S) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.52–6.12 (9H, m, Ar-H), 5.41 (1H, s, -NH), 4.15 (2H, s, -NH₂) ppm.

General procedure for the preparation of thiazolidinones 4a, 4b :

Conventional method : A mixture of **3a/3b** (0.01 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.01 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (15 mL) with a trace of acetic anhydride (2.0 mL) was refluxed for 7–8 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The solid that separated out was filtered and purified by recrystallization from glacial acetic acid to give **4a** and **4b** in 64–69% yields.

Microwave method : A mixture of **3a/3b** (0.01 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.01 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.01 mol), glacial acetic acid (15.0 mL) and acetic anhy-

dride (2.0 mL) was subjected to microwave irradiation in an open Erlenmeyer flask for 5–8 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice cold water. The solid thus separated was filtered, washed with water and finally crystallized from glacial acetic acid in 75–77% yields.

2-*{[Benzylidene-5-oxo-2-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-1-yl]imino}-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one* (**4a**, $C_{19}H_{14}N_4O_2S$) :

White powder (77%); m.p. 190 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3300 (N–H), 3100 (C–H, aromatic), 1720 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 1650 (C=O, imidazolinone), 1630 (C=N), 1562 (C–N), 685 (C–S–C) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 7.90–6.82 (10H, m, Ar-H), 6.57 (1H, s, exoolefinic=CH), 5.05 (1H, s, -NH), 3.34 (2H, s, -CH₂) ppm.

3-*{[4-Oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene]amino}-2-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (**4b**, $C_{17}H_{12}N_4O_2S$) :

Creemish white powder (75%); m.p. 121 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3310 (N–H), 3065 (C–H, aromatic), 1764 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 1645 (C=O, quinazolinone), 1620 (C=N), 1572 (C–N), 705 (C–S–C) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 8.27–7.21 (9H, m, Ar-H), 5.17 (1H, s, -NH), 2.53 (2H, s, -CH₂) ppm.

General procedure for the preparation of chalcones : (**5a**¹, **5a**², **5b**¹, **5b**²) :

Conventional method : A mixture of **4a/4b** (0.001 mol) the aromatic aldehyde (0.001 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.002 mol) in glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 3–5 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to attain room temperature and treated with cold water. The solid thus separated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from glacial acetic acid to give **5** in 63–73% yields.

Microwave method : Compound **4a/4b** was suspended in a minimum quantity of ethanol. The aromatic aldehyde (0.001 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.002 mol) and glacial acetic acid (10.0 mL) were added and the mixture was irradiated for 1.50–2.50 min. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and then poured into ice cold water. The solid separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from glacial acetic acid to give **5** in 76–87% yields.

2-*{[Benzylidene-5-oxo-2-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-1-yl]imino}-5-(4-fluoro benzylidene)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one* (**5a**¹, $C_{26}H_{17}N_4O_2SF$) :

Yellow powder (87%); m.p. 184 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3302 (N–H), 3028 (C–H, aromatic), 1705 (C=O,

thiazolidinone), 1638 (C=O, imidazolinone), 1628–1634 (C=N), 1567 (C–N), 1101 (C–F), 817 (Ar-H, 1,4-disubs.), 705 (C–S–C) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 7.71–6.65 (10H, m, Ar-H), 6.59 (1H, s, CH₂), 6.30 (1H, s, exoolefinic=CH), 4.94 (1H, s, -NH) ppm.

2-*{[Benzylidene-5-oxo-2-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-1-yl]imino}-5-(3-nitro benzylidene)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one* (**5a**², $C_{26}H_{17}N_5O_4S$) :

Yellow powder (85%); m.p. 195 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3298 (N–H), 3060 (C–H, aromatic), 1700 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 1640 (C=O, imidazolinone), 1615–1635 (C=N), 1558 (C–N), 1550, 1350 (asymmetrical symmetrical NO₂), 680 (C–S–C) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 7.94–6.73 (10H, m, Ar-H), 6.52 (1H, s, CH₂), 6.66 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 5.20 (1H, s, -NH) ppm.

3-*{[5-(4-Fluorobenzylidene)-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene]amino}-2-phenylquinazolin-4-(3H)-one* (**5b**¹, $C_{24}H_{15}N_4O_2SF$) :

Pale yellow powder (76%); m.p. 178 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3320 (N–H), 3080 (C–H, aromatic), 1710 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 1654 (C=O, quinazolinone), 1618–1635 (C=N), 1576 (C–N), 1110 (C–F), 815 (Ar-H, 1,4-disubs.), 700 (C–S–C) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 7.41–7.08 (9H, m, Ar-H), 6.44 (1H, s, CH₂), 5.16 (1H, s, -NH) ppm.

3-*{[5-(3-Nitrobenzylidene)-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene]amino}-2-phenylquinazolin-4-(3H)-one* (**5b**², $C_{24}H_{15}N_5O_4S$) :

Pale yellow powder (83%); m.p. 195 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3315 (N–H), 3072 (C–H, aromatic), 1698 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 1640 (C=O, quinazolinone), 1622–1630 (C=N), 1580 (C–N), 1550, 1345 (asymmetrical, symmetrical NO₂) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 7.23–6.51 (9H, m, Ar-H), 6.46 (1H, s, CH₂), 5.33 (1H, s, -NH) ppm.

General procedure for the preparation of isoxazoles (**6a**¹, **6a**², **6b**¹, **6b**²) :

Conventional method : A mixture of **5a**¹, **5a**²/**5b**¹, **5b**² (0.001 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.001 mol) was taken in absolute ethanol. Two drops of KOH (2%) were added slowly to the solution. It was refluxed for 10–12 h. The reaction mixture was kept overnight and then the solution was poured into water. The resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallized from EtOH in 59–67% yields.

Microwave method : To a mixture of **5a**¹, **5a**²/**5b**¹,

5b² (0.001 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.001 mol) in ethanol (15.0 ml), two drops of KOH (2%) were added and this mixture was irradiated for 4–6 min and kept over night. The solution was poured into ice cold water. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed and crystallized from EtOH in 70–83% yields.

5-Benzylidene-3-{{3-(4-fluorophenyl)-3,3a-dihydro-[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazol-5-(6H)-ylidene}amino}-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one (6a¹, C₂₆H₁₈N₅O₂SF) :

White powder (79%); m.p. 226 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3250 (N–H), 3034 (C–H, aromatic), 1674 (C=O), 1625–1632 (C=N), 1569 (C–N), 1120 (C–F), 1075 (C–O), 900 (N–O), 820 (Ar–H, 1,4-disubs.), 710 (C–S–C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.68–6.50 (10H, m, Ar–H), 6.31 (1H, s, exoolefinic=CH), 4.81 (1H, s, NH), 4.60 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.52 (1H, d, CH_b) ppm; MS : *m/z* 483 [M]⁺, 236 [C₁₀H₇N₃OSF]⁺, 170 [C₁₀H₆N₂O]⁺, 157 [C₉H₅N₂O]⁺, 141 [C₄H₃N₃OS]⁺, 123 [C₇H₄OF]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 95 [C₆H₄F]⁺, 93 [C₄HN₂O]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 55 [C₃H₃O]⁺, 30 [NO]⁺, 27 [C₂H₃]⁺.

5-Benzylidene-3-{{3-(3-nitrophenyl)-3,3a-dihydro-[1,3]thiazole[4,5-c]isoxazol-5-(6H)-ylidene}amino}-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one (6a², C₂₆H₁₈N₆O₄S) :

White powder (70%); m.p. 207 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3254 (N–H), 3012 (C–H, aromatic), 1678 (C=O), 1625–1620 (C=N), 1564 (C–N), 1545, 1350 (NO₂), 1080 (C–O), 902 (N–O), 690, 770 (Ar–H, 1,3-disubs.), 714 (C–S–C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.86–6.92 (10H, m, Ar–H), 6.47 (1H, s, exoolefinic=CH), 5.22 (1H, s, NH), 4.91 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.48 (1H, d, CH_b) ppm; MS : *m/z* 510 [M]⁺, 263 [C₁₀H₇N₄O₃S]⁺, 170 [C₁₀H₆N₂O]⁺, 157 [C₉H₅N₂O]⁺, 141 [C₄H₃N₃OS]⁺, 150 [C₇H₄NO₃]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 122 [C₆H₄NO₂]⁺, 93 [C₄HN₂O]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 46 [NO₂]⁺, 55 [C₃H₃O]⁺, 30 [NO]⁺, 28 [CO]⁺, 27 [C₂H₃]⁺.

3-{{3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazol-5-(6H)-ylidene}amino}-2-phenylquinazolin-4-(3H)-one (6b¹, C₂₄H₁₆N₅O₂SF) :

Pale yellow powder (83%); m.p. 192 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3338 (N–H), 3110 (C–H, aromatic), 1665 (C=O), 1615–1630 (C=N), 1620 (C–N), 1078 (C–F), 1060 (C–O), 898 (N–O), 820 (Ar–H, 1,4-disubs.), 708 (C–S–C str.) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.41–7.20 (9H, m, Ar–H), 5.25 (1H, s, NH), 4.55 (1H, s, N–H), 4.52 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.43 (1H, d, CH_b) ppm; MS : *m/z* 457 [M]⁺, 236 [C₁₀H₇N₃OSF]⁺, 141 [C₄H₃N₃OS]⁺, 123 [C₇H₄OF]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 95 [C₆H₄F]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 55

[C₃H₃O]⁺, 30 [NO]⁺, 30 [CH₄N]⁺, 28 [CO]⁺, 28 [N₂]⁺.

3-{{3-(3-Nitrophenyl)-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazol-5-(6H)-ylidene}amino}-2-phenylquinazolin-4-(3H)-one (6b², C₂₄H₁₆N₆O₄S) :

Pale yellow powder (74%); m.p. 189 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3290 (N–H), 3102 (C–H, aromatic), 1665 (C=O), 1620–1635 (C=N), 1570 (C–N), 1570–1365 (NO₂), 1071 (C–O), 895 (N–O), 700, 760 (Ar–H, 1,3-disubs.), 705 (C–S–C str.) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.41–6.80 (9H, m, Ar–H), 5.49 (1H, s, NH), 4.47 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.40 (1H, d, CH_b) ppm; MS : *m/z* 484 [M]⁺, 236 [C₁₀H₇N₃OSF]⁺, 141 [C₄H₃N₃OS]⁺, 150 [C₇H₄NO₃]⁺, 122 [C₆H₄NO₂]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 55 [C₃H₃O]⁺, 46 [NO₂]⁺, 30 [NO]⁺, 30 [CH₄N]⁺, 28 [CO]⁺, 28 [N₂]⁺.

General procedure for the preparation of pyrazoles (7a¹, 7a², 7b¹, 7b²) :

Conventional method : **5a¹, 5a²/5b¹, 5b²** (0.001 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.001 mol) were dissolved in ethanol. After the addition of two drops of pyridine the mixture was refluxed for 14–16 h. After concentrating the reaction mixture, it was cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The solid obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallized from EtOH giving 59–64% yields.

Microwave method : To a solution of **5a¹, 5a²/5b¹, 5b²** (0.001 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.001 mol) in ethanol, two drops of pyridine were added and the mixture was irradiated for 4–5 min under microwave irradiation. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into the ice-cold water. The solid thus separated was filtered, washed and crystallized from EtOH to give 69–76% yields.

5-Benzylidene-3-{{3-(4-fluorophenyl)-2,3,3a,6-tetrahydro-5H-pyrazolo[3,4-d][1,3]thiazolo-5-ylidene}amino}-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one (7a¹, C₂₆H₁₉N₆OSF) :

Yellow powder (76%); m.p. 231 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3330 (N–H), 3080 (C–H, aromatic), 1660 (C=O), 1622–1638 (C=N), 1575 (C–N), 1109 (C–F), 817 (Ar–H, 1,4-disubs.), 712 (C–S–C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.21–6.45 (10H, m, Ar–H), 6.24 (1H, s, exoolefinic=CH), 6.20 (1H, s, N–NH), 4.95 (1H, s, -NH), 4.58 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.54 (1H, d, CH_b) ppm; MS : *m/z* 482 [M]⁺, 235 [C₁₀H₈N₄SF]⁺, 170 [C₁₀H₆N₂O]⁺, 157 [C₉H₅N₂O]⁺, 140 [C₄H₄N₄S]⁺, 123 [C₇H₄OF]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 95 [C₆H₄F]⁺, 93 [C₄HN₂O]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 28 [N₂]⁺,

28 [CO]⁺, 27 [C₂H₃]⁺.

5-Benzylidene-3-[[3-(3-nitrophenyl)-2,3,3a,6-tetrahydro-5H-pyrazolo[3,4-d][1,3]thiazolo-5-ylidene]amino]-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one (**7a**², C₂₆H₁₉N₇O₃S) :

White powder (69%); m.p. 190 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3320 (N-H), 3072 (C-H, aromatic), 1650 (C=O), 1626–1630 (C=N), 1565 (C-N), 1545, 1350 (NO₂), 675, 765 (Ar-H, 1,3-disubs.), 709 (C-S-C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 8.02–7.33 (10H, m, Ar-H), 6.61 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 6.25 (1H, s, N-NH), 5.24 (1H, s, -NH), 4.43 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.52 (1H, d, CH_b) ppm; MS : m/z 509 [M]⁺, 262 [C₁₀H₈N₅O₂S]⁺, 170 [C₁₀H₆N₂O]⁺, 157 [C₉H₅N₂O]⁺, 140 [C₄H₄N₄S]⁺, 150 [C₇H₄NO₃]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 122 [C₆H₄NO₂]⁺, 93 [C₄HN₂O]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 46 [NO₂]⁺, 28 [N₂]⁺.

3-[[3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-2,3,3a,6-tetrahydro-5H-pyrazolo-[3,4-d][1,3]thiazolo-5-ylidene]amino]-2-phenylquinazolin-4-(3H)-one (**7b**¹, C₂₄H₁₇N₆OSF) :

White powder (74%); m.p. 160 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3310 (N-H), 3110 (C-H, aromatic), 1640 (C=O), 1620–1635 (C=N), 1510 (C-N), 1047 (C-F), 833 (Ar-H, 1,4-disubs.), 709 (C-S-C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 7.26–6.42 (9H, m, Ar-H), 6.15 (1H, s, N-NH), 5.11 (1H, s, -NH), 4.48 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.50 (1H, d, CH_b) ppm; MS : m/z 456 [M]⁺, 235 [C₁₀H₈N₄SF]⁺, 140 [C₄H₄N₄S]⁺, 123 [C₇H₄OF]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 95 [C₆H₄F]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 32 [N₂H₄]⁺, 30 [CH₄N]⁺, 28 [CO]⁺, 28 [N₂]⁺, 27 [C₂H₃]⁺.

3-[[3-(3-Nitrophenyl)-2,3,3a,6-tetrahydro-5H-pyrazolo-[3,4-d][1,3]thiazolo-5-ylidene]amino]-2-phenylquinazolin-4-(3H)-one (**7b**², C₂₄H₁₇N₇O₃S) :

White powder (73%); m.p. 183 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3318 (N-H), 3100 (C-H, aromatic), 1645 (C=O), 1620–1635 (C=N), 1572 (C-N), 1545, 1355 (NO₂), 685, 795 (Ar-H, 1,3-disubs.), 715 (C-S-C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 7.45–6.54 (9H, m, Ar-H), 6.02 (1H, s, N-NH), 4.93 (1H, s, -NH), 4.56 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.55 (1H, d, CH_b) ppm; MS : m/z 483 [M]⁺, 262 [C₁₀H₈N₅O₂S]⁺, 140 [C₄H₄N₄S]⁺, 150 [C₇H₄NO₃]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 122 [C₆H₄NO₂]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 46 [NO₂]⁺, 32 [N₂H₄]⁺, 30 [CH₄N]⁺, 28 [CO]⁺, 28 [N₂]⁺, 27 [C₂H₃]⁺.

General procedure for the preparation of pyrimidines (**8a**¹, **8a**², **8b**¹, **8b**²) :

Conventional method : A mixture of **5a**¹, **5a**²/**5b**¹, **5b**² (0.001 mol) and urea (0.001 mol) in ethanol with a

trace of acetic acid was refluxed for 15–17 h. After cooling the reaction mixture was neutralized with 5% NaOH solution. The solid that separated out was filtered, washed several times with water and crystallized from acetic acid to give 62–69% yields.

Microwave method : To a mixture of **5a**¹, **5a**²/**5b**¹, **5b**² (0.001 mol) and urea (0.001 mol) in ethanol (5.0 mL), 5 drops of acetic acid were added and irradiated for 5–6 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and neutralized with 5% NaOH solution. The solid product was filtered, washed several times with water and crystallized from acetic acid to give 74–76% yields.

2-[[4-Benzylidene-5-oxo-2-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-1-yl]imino]-7-(4-fluorophenyl)-2,3,7,7a-tetrahydro-[1,3]thiazole[4,5-d]pyrimidine-5(6H)-one (**8a**¹, C₂₇H₁₉N₆O₂SF) :

White powder (74%); m.p. 184 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3332 (N-H), 3010 (C-H, aromatic), 1715 (C=O, pyrimidine), 1640 (C=O, imidazolone), 1625–1630 (C=N), 1572 (C-N), 1030 (C-F), 823 (Ar-H, 1,4-disubs.), 718 (C-S-C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 9.41 (1H, s, CONH), 7.27–6.55 (10H, m, Ar-H), 6.22 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 4.50 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.44 (1H, d, CH_b), 3.26 (1H, s, -NH) ppm; MS : m/z 510 [M]⁺, 190 [C₁₀H₇N₂OF]⁺, 170 [C₁₀H₆N₂O]⁺, 157 [C₉H₅N₂O]⁺, 123 [C₇H₄OF]⁺, 123 [C₇H₄OF]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 95 [C₆H₄F]⁺, 93 [C₄HN₂O]⁺, 92 [C₄H₃N₂O]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 60 [N₂H₄CO]⁺, 44 [CONH₂]⁺, 28 [CO]⁺, 27 [C₂H₃]⁺.

2-[[4-Benzylidene-5-oxo-2-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-imidazol-1-yl]imino]-7-(3-nitrophenyl)-2,3,7,7a-tetrahydro-[1,3]thiazole[4,5-d]pyrimidine-5(6H)-one (**8a**², C₂₇H₁₉N₇O₄S) :

White powder (76%); m.p. 207 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3322 (N-H), 3075 (C-H, aromatic), 1715 (C=O, pyrimidine), 1647 (C=O, imidazolone), 1623–1638 (C=N), 1557 (C-N), 1545, 1345 (NO₂), 690, 810 (Ar-H, 1,3-disubs.), 720 (C-S-C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 9.35 (1H, s, CONH), 7.04–8.08 (10H, m, Ar-H), 6.41 (1H, s, exoolefinic =CH), 4.49 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.60 (1H, d, CH_b), 3.52 (1H, s, -NH) ppm; MS : m/z 537 [M]⁺, 217 [C₁₀H₇N₃O₃]⁺, 170 [C₁₀H₆N₂O]⁺, 157 [C₉H₅N₂O]⁺, 150 [C₇H₄NO₃]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 122 [C₆H₄NO₂]⁺, 93 [C₄HN₂O]⁺, 92 [C₄H₃N₂O]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 60 [N₂H₄CO]⁺, 46 [NO₂]⁺, 44 [CONH₂]⁺, 28 [CO]⁺, 27 [C₂H₃]⁺.

3-[[7-(4-Fluorophenyl)-5-oxo-5,6,7,7a-tetrahydro-[1,

3]-thiazolo-[4,5-d]pyrimidin-2(3H)-ylidene]amino}-2-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (8b¹, C₂₅H₁₇N₆O₂SF) :

White powder (75%); m.p. 183 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3348 (N-H), 3120 (C-H, aromatic), 1703 (C=O, pyrimidine), 1650 (C=O, imidazolone), 1615-1630 (C=N), 1560 (C-N), 1020 (C-F), 818 (Ar-H, 1,4-disubs.), 710 (C-S-C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 9.24 (1H, s, CONH), 7.31-6.81 (9H, m, Ar-H), 4.50 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.48 (1H, d, CH_b), 3.25 (1H, s, -NH) ppm; MS : m/z 484 [M]⁺, 190 [C₁₀H₇N₂OF]⁺, 123 [C₇H₄OF]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 95 [C₆H₄F]⁺, 92 [C₄H₃N₂O]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 60 [N₂H₄CO]⁺, 44 [CONH₂]⁺, 30 [CH₄N]⁺.

3-{{[7-(3-Nitrophenyl)-5-oxo-5,6,7,7a-tetrahydro-[1,3]-thiazolo-[4,5-d]pyrimidin-2(3H)-ylidene]amino}-2-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (8b², C₂₅H₁₇N₇O₄S) :

White powder (74%); m.p. 195 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3350 (N-H), 3125 (C-H, aromatic), 1703 (C=O, pyrimidine), 1640 (C=O, imidazolone), 1625-1635 (C=N), 1555 (C-N), 1525, 1392 (-NO₂), 710, 790 (Ar-H, 1,3-disubs.), 684 (C-S-C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 9.06 (1H, s, CONH), 7.56-6.62 (9H, m, Ar-H), 4.64 (1H, d, CH_a), 3.47 (1H, d, CH_b), 3.23 (1H, s, -NH) ppm; MS : m/z 511 [M]⁺, 217 [C₁₀H₇N₃O₃]⁺, 150 [C₇H₄NO₃]⁺, 103 [C₇H₅N]⁺, 122 [C₆H₄NO₂]⁺, 92 [C₄H₃N₂O]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 60 [N₂H₄CO]⁺, 46 [NO₂]⁺, 44 [CONH₂]⁺, 43 [C₂H₅N]⁺, 30 [CH₄N]⁺.

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